

Research Article

“Comfert”- A Sustainable Gardening Revolution of an Integrated Compostable Pot and Fertiliser Inserter

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Abstract: Household gardening is perceived as a positive factor in a greener planet, fruitful community, and human well-being. However, contemporary gardening tools and solutions such as plastic planting pots and conventional fertilisers are one of the causes of today’s environmental crisis. It can produce soil pollution, landfill waste, greenhouse emissions, and health risks. Moreover, these tools are often complicated and time-consuming to be incorporated into gardening routines. Therefore, there is an emergence of innovating a sustainable but practical gardening solution that could potentially mitigate adverse environmental effects, streamline gardening practices and cultivate a community of healthy gardening practices. This paper will propose a novel hybrid gardening product called “Comfert”- the seamless integration of a compostable pot and fertiliser inserter. Comfert is developed with biodegradable materials that are naturally derived and without any plastic contents and harsh chemicals. This innovation strives to tackle environmental and functionality issues by enabling gardeners to have a hassle and mess-free gardening experience while actively protecting Mother Nature. The findings show that Comfert can improve gardening practices significantly and supports the growth of all plants. Simultaneously, it reduces a considerable amount of surplus waste and pollutants thanks to its unique design and eco-friendly formulation. The commercialisation potential is promising as the target market of this easy-to-use, eco-friendly product is household gardening enthusiasts, sustainable advocates, and even gardening newbies who want to enhance and improve their gardening practices while saving the earth one step at a time.

Keywords: sustainable gardening, gardening practices, compostable, nature-derived, user-friendly

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1. INTRODUCTION

Household gardening is an activity that is often celebrated and promoted for its therapeutic exercise, self-provision, and way of adding a touch of greenery at home and in the neighbourhood. During the COVID-19 lockdown pandemic, many Malaysians spend more time gardening and horticultural activities as a pastime (COVID-19 Pandemic Sees More Malaysians Getting Into Home Gardening, 2021). Furthermore, it encourages more people to plant their fruits and vegetables in their

gardens, thus providing economic and health benefits (Sharif et al., 2024). Most importantly, gardening inspires society to get together as a community. Green or flowery plants preserve agricultural heritage and contribute to a sustainable urban future amidst climate change. Nevertheless, contemporary gardening tools and solutions are increasingly invasive to the environment.

Traditional planting pots, often made of ceramic or clay, have been increasingly replaced by plastic pots due to their lightweight, durability, and affordability. However, plastic planting pots contribute to significant environmental danger because plastics are made from nonrenewable petroleum sources (Sondhi, 2022). Though they are functional for growing plants, these pots are frequently discarded after a single use, adding to the plastic pollution crisis. The challenge lies in finding sustainable alternatives or improving the lifecycle of traditional planting pots to reduce reliance on plastic and mitigate its environmental impact.

Additionally, conventional fertilisers are synthetic fertilisers that are locally available in the market (Colipano & Cagayan, 2022). It has all of the micro and macronutrients to support plant growth. However, studies have also shown that conventional fertilisers lead to soil, water, and air pollution due to high levels of harsh chemicals that cause eutrophication increases, which harm the ecosystem and human health (Ayilalath et al., 2021). Conventional fertilisers have presented alarming environmental concerns. Furthermore, the practicability of conventional fertiliser is still being determined. This is because gardeners may or may not know what kind and how much it should be used. The surplus and shortage of fertiliser usage are potentially the reasons why plants are decaying and infertility of the soil.

In pursuing sustainable agriculture and gardening, innovative solutions are crucial to reducing environmental impact and enhancing efficiency. This paper introduces an approach that integrates compostable pots with fertiliser inserter, addressing waste reduction and optimised nutrient delivery. The proposed solution is to minimise plastic waste and make the planting and fertilisation process more efficient. The compostable pots decompose naturally, contributing to soil health, while the integrated fertiliser inserter ensures precise nutrient application. This introduction sets the stage for discussing how this dual-function system can revolutionise household gardening practices, offering a greener, more efficient alternative to traditional methods and maintaining its user-friendly characteristics. That is how Comfert was born: the best of both worlds of Com, the compostable pot and Fert, the fertiliser inserter combined.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Compostable Pot

According to Tomadoni et al. (2020), biodegradable pots constitute an excellent alternative for growing plants since they can be fully compostable in soil and improve plant growth and development compared to traditional non-biodegradable plastic pots. Compostable pots are made from biodegradable materials like plant fibres, a sustainable replacement for conventional plastic pots. They act as a barrier to support plant growth.

Recycled paper, cardboard, and coconut husk are cut into small pieces and soaked in water for twenty-four hours. This soaking process softens the materials, making them easier to blend. After soaking, drain the excess water and transfer the softened materials into a blender. Blend until the mixture reaches a smooth, pulpy consistency. Once blended, remove any remaining water to achieve a workable texture. Next, mould the blended pulp into pot shapes using an actual planting pot as a mould to ensure the correct size and form. To improve the pots' durability and hardness, cover the moulded pots' surface with flour. Allow the pots to dry completely in a well-ventilated area, which will take three days. After thoroughly drying and hardening, the pots are carefully removed from the pot.

2.2 Fertiliser Inserter

Excessive use of chemical fertilisers is one of the most common causes of environmental pollution (Chiurciu et al., 2023). Furthermore, excessive or insufficient fertiliser use will prevent the plant from germinating; leaves will be burned and wilted, and roots will be weakened. The fertiliser inserter is formulated with recycled, naturally derived materials: moulded pulp, coco peat, and rice husk, and enriched with a nutrition supplement of Nitrogen, Phosphorus, and Potassium (NPK).

The fertiliser inserter is made by cutting the moulded pulp into small sizes and soaking it in water for 30 minutes before draining it. The coco peat and rice husk to vinegar is a ratio of 3:1. Next, the moulded pulp, cocopeat, rice husk and crushed egg shells are mixed into a pulpy mixture. A mould is prepared to mould the mixture to a pot shape. Dry for thirty minutes. Add organic soil with 1 part of the comfrey meal. Mix it with a small amount of water until it becomes a paste. The paste is then applied on top of the moulded mixture. Dry it for a day. Then, holes are created in the bottom of the inserter to make drainage holes. Lastly, the inserter is left to dry for two days before removing it from the mould. Different sizes may have different drying durations.

2.3 The first-ever integration of a Compostable Pot and a Fertiliser Inserter

The fertiliser should be half the size of the compostable pots to fit easily. It is meant to be integrated so that gardeners can directly use it with their preferred soil and seeds. The functionality of the compostable and the fertiliser worked simultaneously to cultivate a healthier plant while producing less waste and toxic accumulation.

Figure 1: Instructions to use Comfert

3. FINDINGS

Comfert is not just an ordinary pot; it is the perfect dynamic duo gardening solution that brings joy to gardeners when plants grow lusciously and is eco-friendly. The compostable pot can withstand

moisture and supports the plant, fertiliser inserter and soil. Furthermore, it enables gardeners to avoid using plastic pots. Plastic pots stop bacterial activities in the soil; however, compostable pots do not (Jaya et al., 2023). The compostable pot is also biodegradable. Hence, it will not cause further plastic waste that can harm the environment.

The fertiliser inserter has immensely assisted gardeners in their plants to germinate faster and grow healthier. It simplifies fertiliser use so that gardeners can no longer track fertilisation schedules. This promotes sustainability practices at a convenience. The chemical-free fertiliser inserter ensures that plants bloom successfully and survive longer due to its powerful nature-derived properties that all plants love. Along with the drainage holes in the fertiliser inserter, the feature does not perish from overwatering and also overwatering.

Gardeners just need to remember to water the plants and put the plants in direct sunlight. Therefore, Comfert ensures its problem statement, in which new or existing gardening lovers may feel challenged about whether they have applied the proper process and equipment to plant their seeds. This shows that Comfert saves the day, addressing challenges and struggles head-on by providing precise and straightforward instructions designed to unravel the beauty of gardening. The innovation offers user-friendly guidelines that break down complex steps into straightforward stages in which our product will “kill two birds with one stone”. Having an all-in-one gardening solution ready for beginners will encourage and foster a sense of accomplishment for gardening lovers. Comfert’s spotlights its time and cost-efficiency benefits to make gardening more accessible and affordable. Comfert is also suitable for kids with parental supervision from age 5 with an interest in gardening.

4. DISCUSSION

Comfert is a unique gardening solution that streamlines household gardening practices, nourishes and strengthens plants, and revolutionises sustainable gardening targeting. The innovation has emerged as a transformative gardening solution that improves gardening practices, as planting can sometimes be tedious and tiring. With Comfert, gardeners can personalise their pots using their preferred seeds and soil, enabling them to have and fulfil their specific plant needs and desires. Thus, gardeners can create a sense of accomplishment through efficient and effective household gardening.

This can be translated with Comfert’s value proposition as a foundation of transforming the gardening experience for a diverse range of users, typically focusing on its target market, novice gardeners or those just beginning their horticultural journey to evaluate their gardening practices. The product’s approach centres on creating a user-friendly, efficient, and enjoyable gardening experience that aligns with the needs and aspirations of the implemented target market’s satisfaction.

This innovation proves that Comfert possesses the power to be a superhero for mother nature due to our product consisting of a combination of a composable pot and a fertiliser inserter, providing valuable solutions that enrich the lives of our gardener lovers and contribute to a greener, more sustainable world one pot at a time. Comfert sets are to be widely accessible by distributing through various retail outlets and available on prominent online shopping platforms. (Sheikh et al., 2024) quoted that emphasising the importance of educational and awareness initiatives is crucial to maximise the potential of new gardening systems to advocate for sustainable agricultural practices. Consequently, Comfert will participate in gardening campaigns that educate the public on the importance of using sustainable gardening products. The targeted audiences are household gardeners, sustainable advocates and gardening newbies. Comfert anticipates increasing the interest in eco-friendly and user-friendly gardening practices for society and the nation.

Figure 2. Comfert's logo

Figure 3. Comfert

Figure 4: Inside of Comfert

5. CONCLUSION

Comfert aims to be kinder to the environment in the hopes that we can help save the world for future generations. There is a call to action to lead a sustainable life. Overall, the introduction of Comfert is a groundbreaking approach to sustainable gardening practices and solutions that fosters the community to make earth-friendly choices with outside spaces. It will adopt a multifaceted promotional strategy to maximise brand visibility and engagement across various platforms and demographics. Future enhancements could encompass such as improved fertiliser formulas and compostable design that could significantly positively impact the plant, environment and users. As the saying goes, one small step makes significant changes. It is compulsory to make small changes to meet the needs and keep everything functioning for as long as possible. Choose Comfert. Let us build a community that "Comferts" their souls through gardening!

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References

- Ayilalath, A., KR, R., & Nill, J. (2021). Fate of the conventional fertilizers in environment. In Elsevier eBooks (pp. 25–39). <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-819555-0.00002-9>
- Chiurciu, I., Dana, D., Firatoiu, A., Voicu, V., Chereji, A., & Chereji, I. J. (2023). THE RESEARCH ON NON-CONVENTIONAL FOLIAR FERTILIZERS WITH PROTEIN HYDROLYSATES APPLIED TO MAIZE CROP. *Annals of the University of Craiova - Agriculture Montanology Cadastre Series*, 52(1), 380–383.
- Colipano, J. A., & Cagasan, U. (2022). A review on the impact of organic, conventional and nano fertilizer application in crop production. *Eurasian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 6(2), 101-109. <https://doi.org/10.52846/aamc.v52i1.1363>
- Covid-19 pandemic sees more Malaysians getting into home gardening. (2021, December). *The Borneo Post*. <https://www.theborneopost.com/2021/12/22/covid-19-pandemic-sees-more-malaysians-getting-into-home-gardening/>

- Jaya, J. D., Nugroho, A., Elma, M., & Sunardi, S. (2023). Review on biodegradable pot: A new promising approach for sustainable agriculture. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0118270>
- Sharif, S. M., Ujang, N., Shukor, S. F. A., & Maruthaveeran, S. (2024, July). Beyond Growing Crops: How Community Gardening Shapes the Residents' Meaning of Participation. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 1361, No. 1, p. 012045). IOP Publishing.
- Sheikh, P. P., Akash, A., Rahman, M., & Khan, T. (2024). An Arduino based automated gardening system for efficient and sustainable plant growth. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*. <https://doi.org/10.56726/irjmets49294>
- Sondhi, S. (2022). Applications of Bioplastic in Composting Bags and Planting Pots. *Handbook of Bioplastics and Biocomposites Engineering Applications*, 2nd Edition, 605–617. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119160182.ch28>
- Tomadoni, B., Merino, D., Casalengué, C., & Alvarez, V. (2020). Biodegradable materials for planting pots. In *Materials research foundations* (pp. 85–103). <https://doi.org/10.21741/9781644900659-4>